

APPLICATION OF ELECTRODIALYSIS TOWARDS THE 1-METHYL-3-OCTYLIMIDAZOLIUM CHLORIDE IONIC LIQUID RECOVERY

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Abstract: Due to the wide applications of ionic liquids (ILs) in a variety of industrial fields, their degree of toxicity, and a high price, the development of ILs recovery methods is very important. One of the membrane processes that can be used for ILs recovery from aqueous solutions is electrodialysis (ED). ED is a process capable of desalting the solution in the diluate compartment and concentrating the ionic salt in the concentrate compartment. Thus, in this study, research on 1-methyl-3-octylimidazolium chloride ([OMIM]Cl) recovery from wastewater by ED is presented. The influence of the initial [OMIM]Cl concentration, the voltage, and the linear flow velocity on the effective ([OMIM]Cl) recovery was examined. Also, the characteristics of ion-exchange membranes (IEMs) before and after ED and chemical stability of the recovered [OMIM]Cl were determined.

The [OMIM]Cl recovery was carried out using an EDR-Z/10-0.8 module (MemBrain, Czech Republic) with an effective single membrane area of 64 cm². There were 5 pairs of the IEMs. All process solutions were recirculated using a peristaltic pump (Masterflex L/S, Cole-Parmer, United States). Research included a series of experiments on the effect of operating parameters, such as IL concentration (from 0.05 to 0.25 mol/L), applied voltage (from 5 to 10 V), and linear flow velocity (from 1 to 3 cm/s), on the ED performance. The concentrations of [OMIM]Cl in diluate and concentrate solutions were analyzed using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-2700i, Japan). The surface morphology of IEMs before and after ED were investigated by scanning electron microscopy (JEOL JSM-7610F Plus, Japan), and also by an atomic force microscopy (AFM, CoreAFM Nanosurf) with HQ:CSC17/Al BS contact mode AFM probe (MikroMasch). The chemical stability of the recovered [OMIM]Cl was determined by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR).

It was found that the [OMIM]Cl concentration, applied voltage drop, linear flow velocity, and membrane type had influence on the [OMIM]Cl recovery by ED method. It was noted that the [OMIM]Cl recovery and concentration degree increased with increasing [OMIM]Cl concentration in the initial diluate solution. The highest ED efficiency for the recovery and concentration of [OMIM]Cl was obtained at an applied potential of 10 V, a 2 cm/s linear flow velocity, and 0.2 M IL in the feed solution. Furthermore, it was shown that the chemical structure of the recovered [OMIM]Cl solution did not differ in comparison to the fresh [OMIM]Cl solution.

Keywords: ionic liquids, 1-methyl-3-octylimidazolium chloride, electrodialysis, ILs recovery.

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